

PRODUCTIVITY AND MARKET INDICATORS OF HOLSTIN CATTLE.

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Abstract: One of the important factors for the rapid development of production in the livestock sector is the creation of favorable feeding conditions, taking into account the biological needs of animals. The work carried out in this regard requires in-depth knowledge of their character traits and vital needs. This article provides information on productivity and milk yield indicators of Holstein cattle.

Key words: Holstein breed, bodies, ethology, rumination, feed intake, general activity index.

The results of many scientific studies show that filling a herd of cattle with cows with strong reflexes for food intake creates the basis for the strengthening of these characteristics in the next generations and the creation of easy-to-manage herds of cattle. is a function that determines adaptation to external environmental conditions. In the process of growing them, adaptation to certain feeding conditions is formed in animals based on biological needs. Accordingly, the main character traits are formed in the animals. Currently, the value of the Holstein breed is very high, because it is characterized by the highest milk yield and is used to improve dairy breeds all over the world. It is characterized by good adaptation to different climates and conditions. In the 20th century, the Holstein breed became the dominant breed in world dairy farming. Holstein cows make up 25 million heads or 72% of cows in the world. It is one of the eight most common dairy breeds in the world. In the further development of livestock breeding, improving the breeding, productivity, reproduction, and technological qualities of breeding livestock, creating high-yielding herds, increasing the volume of production of livestock products, wide use of the genetic potential of the productivity of the leading breeds of livestock breeding is important in the world gene pool. Currently, the Holstein is the largest dairy animal in the world. Cows of this breed are distinguished by very high milk yield, unique characteristics of the udder, adaptation to different climatic conditions, high amount of feed, milk products and other valuable breeding characteristics.

Holstein breeding is characterized by ensuring the health, longevity and high reproductive capacity of bulls and high-yielding cows, as well as the intensive elimination of low-yielding animals at an early age. Broad cows are evaluated according to the feed rate, acceptance and payment of their products, the shape of the udder and the speed of milking, the behavior of the herd. it is important to ensure adequate nutrition. One of the factors that ensure the milk yield of cows is full-sided feeding at the level of 6000-8000 kg of milk. Holstein is more demanding than cattle in keeping, feeding and milking technology.

Three groups of mature cows were selected for the study. The first group included cows imported from Germany, the second group included cows from the Netherlands, and the third group included cows from local selection cows. There were 20 cows in each group. Productivity indicators of cows were studied by methods generally obtained in zootechnics. Cows were kept in the same condition, the nutrition was the same, milk yield, live weight and physiological condition were taken into account. Milk yield is one of the main indicators for evaluating the breeding value of cows. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, cows of European breed have a much higher potential for milk production. In cows of group II, milk yield was 141.8 and 157.8 kg, milk fat was 12.8 and 6.3 kg, 4% milk yield was 319.1 and 155.8 compared to cows of group I and III kg was higher. groups. Group I cows milked 106.5 and 19.0 kg more milk per 100 kg of body weight than those of groups II and III. We studied the productivity of cows and the II lactation period. During the II lactation period, milk and fat content in groups I and II are characterized by similar indicators, and milk yield is 169 and 161.5 kg, respectively, and milk yield is 6.6 and 9.1 in cows of group III. increased by kg. 4% milk yield in cows of group I and II was 164 and 226.1 kg more than their counterparts in group III. We continued to study the dynamics of milk production of cows during lactation.

It is important to study the activity of lactation and its stability in assessing the level of adaptability of cows to external environmental conditions and in improving the characteristics of maintaining a stable monthly milk amount during the lactation period. The analysis of the volume of milk production of cows in the first lactation period of animals showed that less milk was obtained from different ages. We studied and analyzed the milk yield of cows in the first lactation of the experimental groups, the results of which are presented in the table. The analysis of the study showed that the milk yield of cows in group I during lactation was 884.6 or 9.3% higher than that of cows in group II, milk fat was 0.07 and 1.71%, and milk protein was 0.01 kg or 0.32%. , the live weight was 16.9 kg or 2.3 percent higher, and the milk yield was 93.4 kg or 7.2 percent higher.

Conclusion: The Holstein breed of European selection has a high genetic potential for milk production and is distinguished by the ability to show it much higher in the specific conditions of the warm climate of Uzbekistan. Various selections of the Holstein breed combine well with high milk yield and fat content. Of the different breeds, the Holstein breed is distinguished by a strong milk type.

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